

SCIENTIFIC METHODS OF RESTAURANT BUSINESS EXPANSION AND MANAGEMENT IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

Qurbonova Malika Axmad qizi

Karshi State University, m Doctoral student of the
2nd stage of the Department of Tourism and Marketing
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13221110>

Abstract: This article examines scientific methods of restaurant business expansion and management in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The development of the restaurant business plays an important role in the economy of the country and makes a significant contribution to the tourism and service industries. The article analyzes scientific methods of effective management of restaurant business, marketing strategies, quality of customer service, innovative approaches and the use of digital technologies. Factors hindering the expansion of the restaurant business and recommendations for their elimination are also given. The article will be useful for restaurant researchers, practitioners and business owners.

Keywords: Restaurant business, Republic of Uzbekistan Management methods, Marketing strategies, Quality of service, Innovative approaches Digital technologies, Business expansion, Economic development Tourism.

The system of catering services in the Republic of Uzbekistan has always changed depending on the reforms implemented in the economy and politics. Currently, catering services are one of the most liquid sectors of the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The annual turnover of a well-known restaurant can be more than 1 million US dollars, and in this case the profit will not be less than 30%. At the same time, the restaurant business requires less capital than, for example, the manufacturing sector.

Among the main reasons for the bankruptcy of the restaurant business are the general economic conditions in the country:

- tendency of the population to save money;
- high cost of renting premises for catering services;
- the cost of imported products;
- the lack of educational programs for the provision of commercial services and their high cost;
- lack of its own developed business infrastructure;
- ban on smoking in public places.

There is no doubt that the service market directly depends on the general economic indicators of the country's development. The ability to pay and the

mentality of the population are important factors that determine the level of spending intended for eating out in cafes, restaurants and other places.

In the laws on innovative activity and state innovation policy in the Republic of Uzbekistan, innovations (innovations) in the market are considered as the final result of innovative activity embodied in the form of a new or improved product for sale. This innovation is also called product innovation. Also, innovation can be implemented by introducing a new technological process that is used in practice or by improving an existing technological process, that is, we are talking about the so-called innovative process. State support of catering enterprises is a necessary component of its development. The development of tourism infrastructure is mentioned in the concept of target programs on "Development of domestic and foreign tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan". This category also includes food establishments.

Currently, the safest and cheapest way to start a restaurant business is franchising. When it comes to franchising, banks almost never refuse to lend. In the near future, food service chains operating in the democratic price segment, which can contribute to business development even in the face of an economic crisis, will receive the greatest income. The goals and aspirations of catering enterprises are not the same in terms of details, they depend on the type of production and the contingent it serves. Thus, some enterprises strive to meet physiological nutritional needs and provide visitors with a pleasant stay, while others focus only on providing food. Restaurateurs are expanding the range of products for sale, so it is necessary to distinguish the directions of development of objects of this format. The specific characteristics of such catering establishments, for example: the degree of emphasis on coffee and coffee drinks, the assortment of coffee cards, the absence or presence of a hot kitchen, the service format.

An innovation in modern culinary art is culinary embellishment, which some consider a form of carving. However, these are two different directions that develop in the same field of activity and use them to develop different methods of decorating dishes. Culinary decoration is a culinary art that allows you to decorate food in a professional manner. It is based on carving, making decorations for vegetables and fruits, making decorations for creating a table from them.

In order to attract and please customers, some restaurateurs are introducing fusion cooking, that is, mixing the traditional tastes of the West and the East. New bar (Fresh-bar) helps to form a culture of communication without

alcohol. The bar menu always includes freshly squeezed and chilled juices, juice cocktails, milk, ice cream, yogurts, fruits, vegetables, as well as tea, coffee, hot chocolate, ice cream.

Particular attention should be paid to innovations in the field of logistics, their use allows to consider the process of material and technical support of economic activity of a catering enterprise as a single system. The main task of this system is to optimize the total costs for the operation of all its elements, taking into account the existing limitations, and at the same time provide a high level of customer service. Logistics developments help to shorten the production time, reduce its cost, and reduce the volume of material and technological reserves. It is necessary to improve the development of logistics for restaurants with a small production volume. Such industries are usually characterized by a small number of labor resources working in the enterprise, and are also limited to production, storage and retail premises. The inventory management system has an innovative nature, which helps to minimize stocks, regardless of external factors, focuses on a large supplier, because a wide network of supermarkets serving small wholesale customers is being created, whose most of them serve them, they belong to restaurant business enterprises.

References:

1. Абдукаримов Б.А ва бошқалар. Оммавий овқатланиш соҳаси иқтисодиёти фанидан масалалар тўплами ва услубий кўрсатмалар. Самарқанд. СамИЦИ, 2012.
2. Kurbanova, M. (2024). INNOVATION IN CATERING ESTABLISHMENTS: BENEFITS AND OBSTACLES. Молодые ученые, 2(8), 4–6. извлечено от <https://in-academy.uz/index.php/yo/article/view/29050>
3. Mukhitdinov Khudayar Suyunovich, Qurbonova Malika Axmad qizi. (2023). PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF CATERING SERVICES IN TOURISM AND HOTELS. THEORETICAL ASPECTS IN THE FORMATION OF PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES, 2(17), 119–128. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8386015>
4. Брагина Л.А. Торговое дело: Экономика, маркетинг, организация. Учебник. М.: ИНФРА –М., 2002.
5. Ergash o'g'li, Qodirov Farrux. "ECONOMETRIC MODELING OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF MEDICAL SERVICES TO THE POPULATION OF THE REGION." Berlin Studies Transnational Journal of Science and Humanities 2.1.1 Economical sciences (2022).
6. Qodirov, F. "Zamonaviy to'lov tizimlari tahlili va elektron pul birliklari. Scienceweb academic papers collection." (2023).

7. Qodirov, Farrux. "Zamonaviy trenajyor va simulyatsiya qiluvchi dasturlarning hozirgi kundagi ahamiyati. Scienceweb academic papers collection." (2023): 1.
8. Qodirov, Farrux. "The place of econometrical modeling of healthcare quality improvement in the digital economy. Scienceweb academic papers collection." (2023): 1.
9. Farrux, Qodirov. "Foreign experience in the development of medical services to the population." Хоразм Маъмун академияси (2022).
10. Qodirov, Farrux. "THE ROLE OF ICT IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF HEALTH SERVICES." RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA JARAYONIGA AXBOROT TEXNOLOGIYALARINI JORIY ETISHDA MA'LUMOTLARNI HIMOYALASH MUAMMOLARI VA YECHIMLARI RESPUBLIKA ILMIY-AMALIY ANJUMANI MA'RUZALAR TO'PLAMI (2022).
11. Qodirov, Farrux. "ECONOMIC-MATHEMATICAL MODELING OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE PROVISION OF MEDICAL SERVICES TO THE POPULATION. Scienceweb academic papers collection." (2023): 1.
12. Qodirov, Farrux. "BUSINESS INNOVATION MODEL OF INCOME AND COSTS FROM THE PROVISION OF MEDICAL SERVICES TO THE POPULATION. Scienceweb academic papers collection." (2023): 1.
13. Qodirov, F. "Optimization of telecommunications power supply systems based on reliability criteria." Science and innovation 2.A12 (2023): 15-20.
14. Ergash o'g'li, Qodirov Farrux. "IMPORTANCE OF KASH-HEALTH WEB PORTAL IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF MEDICAL SERVICES IN THE REGIONS." Conferencea (2022): 80-83.
15. Ergash o'g'li, Qodirov Farrux. "CREATION OF ELECTRONIC MEDICAL BASE WITH THE HELP OF SOFTWARE PACKAGES FOR MEDICAL SERVICES IN THE REGIONS." Conferencea (2022): 128-130.
16. Qodirov, F. E. "Methodological aspects and importance of development of medical services through econometric modeling and forecasting options."
17. Qodirov, F. "Qashqadaryo viloyati aholisiga tibbiy xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlarini rivojlantirishning istiqbollari." O'ZBEKISTON QISHLOQ VA SUV XO'JALIGI» àà «AGRO ILM (2022).
18. Qodirov, F. "Qishloq aholisiga sog'liqni saqlash xizmatlari ko'rsatish tarmoqlari rivojlanish mexanizmining statistik tahlili." Andijon Mashinasozlik Instituti (2022).
19. Qodirov, Farrux. "Aholiga tibbiy xizmat ko'rsatishdan olingan daromad va xarajatlarni imitatsion modeli." Moliya bozorini rivojlantirishning ustuvor

POLAND

CURRENT APPROACHES AND NEW RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCES

International scientific-online conference

POLAND

yo'nalishlari, zamonaviy tendensiyalari va istiqbollari" mavzusidagi Respublika ilmiy-amaliy konferensiyasi materiallar to'plami 11.5 (2022).

20. Qodirov, Farrux. "Development of scientific and technological system of management of industrial enterprises. Scienceweb academic papers collection." (2023): 1.

